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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье системно анализируются онтологические основы ценностных ориентиров в бытии, котором ныне пребывает человечество. Всем известно, что современный мир ныне глобально трансформируется, в дальнейшей судьбе которого велика роль и значение ценностных ориентиров. В этом аспекте, очень важно исследовать и понимать онтологическую природу ценностей, и само бытие как ценность, являющуюся субстанциальной основой всего мироздания.

Ключевые слова: аксиология, тимология, онтологические факторы ценностей, личностные и планетарные ценности, полиценностный мир, самоидентификационный и коммуникативно-сетевой пределы, биосфера, биоценоз, внутренние и внешние оболочки аксиосферы, аксиологические координаты.

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ONTOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE VALUE ATTITUDE TO BEING

ABSTRACT

This article systematically analyzes the ontological foundations of value orientations in the being that humanity currently lives in. Everyone knows that the modern world is now globally transforming, in the future fate of which the role and importance of value orientations is great. In this aspect, it is very important to explore and understand the ontological nature of values, and being itself as a value, which is the substantial basis of the entire universe.

Key words: axiology, thymology, ontological factors of values, personal and planetary values, polysecular world, self-identification and communication-network limits, biosphere, biocenosis, inner and outer shells of the axiosphere, axiological coordinates.

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E-mail: nigoradjurayeva@mail.ru**BORLIQGA QADRIYATLI MUNOSABATNING ONTOLOGIK ASOSLARI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda insoniyat yashayotgan borlig'idagi qadriyatlar oriyentirlarini ontologik asoslari tizimli tahlil qilingan. Hammaga ma'lumki, hozir zamonaviy dunyo global tarzda o'zgarimoqda va qadriyatlar yo'nalishining qiymati va roli keyingi uning taqdiriga ta'siri kattadir. Bu jihatni inobatga olib, aytish kerakki butun borliqning substansional asosi bo'lgan borliqni qadriyat sifatida o'zini va qadriyatlarni ontologik tabiatini o'rganish muximdir.

Kalit so'zlar: aksiologiya, timologiya, qadriyatlarning ontologik omillari, shaxsiy va sayyoraviy qadriyatlar, poliaksiologik dunyo, o'z-o'zini identifikatsiya qilish va aloqa-tarmoq chegaralari, biosfera, biotsenoz, aksiosferaning ichki va tashqi qobiqlari, aksiologik koordinatalar.

Introduction.

The modern world is now globally transforming, and value orientations are of particular importance in it. In particular, value orientations are aimed at strengthening the human personality, are interconnected with the issues of a person's vital energy, his personal qualities, as well as with some important aspects of the planetary worldview. In this aspect, it is very important to explore and understand the ontological nature of values, and being itself as a value, which is the substantial basis of the entire universe.

Moreover, the civilizational transformations that are taking place today also affect people's ideas and their attitude to the values of life. It is important to highlight the obvious fact that the current global problems of human civilization are closely related to the value orientations of humanity. Therefore, today, both for Uzbekistan and for all paradigms of civilizations, it is important to update socio-cultural and intra-social relations.

Degree of study of the problem.

If we turn to the very concept of "axiology", which reveals the understanding of value, then this concept takes its roots from the Greek words "axia" - "value" and "logos" - "teaching". As a special philosophical discipline, axiology arose in the second half of the 19th century in Western Europe, although the category of axiology itself arose in 1902 and was introduced by the French scientist, education reformer Paul Lapi. As a science of values, axiology has come a long historical way of development within the framework of philosophy itself. The crisis of scientific philosophy, which occurred at the beginning of the 19th century, became the reason for the inclusion of an understanding of value from an ontological perspective, and the very understanding of being became closely connected with value attitudes.

Value ideas were in the field of interests of ancient thinkers, in particular, Plato, who introduced the idea of a higher binding principle of sensual being and supersensible - Good; Socrates, Aristotle and others. In the Middle Ages in the West, one can single out the teachings of Boethius, E.Rotterdam, in modern times, the teachings of J.Lock, K.Helvetius, J.J.Rousseau, F.Rabelais, I.Kant and other thinkers. Thus, I.Kant was the first to single out the concept of "good" from the concept of "being", making it the object of scientific research.

It is important to point out that important aspect of static and simplicity that was observed in the social structure before the period of the industrial revolution. Also, the established systems of value orientations themselves existed for a long time. In subsequent years, with the development of the scientific and technological revolution, a dynamic change in modern society takes place, accelerating the process of formation of new values.

Research methods. The article uses the methods of comparative studies, analysis, synthesis, extrapolation, analogy, dialectical, synergetic, organismic methods of scientific knowledge.

Analysis and results. In the sphere of values, such levels of being as social and personal-individual are intertwined, they determine the content of human existence. Thus, a person learns value norms in the process of socialization. Receiving and accepting certain values, he thereby influences the being around him. Demoralization, confusion, state of shock, which are observed both at the level of ministries, rescue services, and at the individual level, have become commonplace aspects of the present. However, a person needs support in order to endure all the hardships of life. Thus, we see that today it is necessary to search for and formulate sources of overcoming hardships. Moreover, another controversial and topical issue in the modern global world is the compatibility of the existence of universal human values with national-ethical, social, religious ones, since fragmentation in these issues in human society is everywhere observed. The question is whether we can talk about universal human values at all if people belonging to different socially and historically established communities invest different content in the value concepts of "honor", "duty", "good", "beautiful", "sacred".

In these ambiguously interpreted concepts of human coexistence and universal human existence, when everything is depreciated in market relations, where everything is bought and sold, there is an undoubted argument: honor is a value for the community, as it strengthens this community as a system from the inside. While betrayal - an anti-value that destroys the integrity and unity of both the community and the person himself, has never been a basis compatible with life and procreation, but was aimed at destruction and chaos in a person's life.

These concepts are accompanied by a number of transformations in the cognitive apparatus of the consciousness of modern man. The reason for these phenomena was the requirements of modern society - a successful person with such features as flexibility, sociability, promiscuity in the means of achieving their goals, even conscience becomes an archaic concept that prevents them from achieving certain benefits for their comfortable life. Thus, a conscientious person is perceived as a "loser" who could not overcome the barriers of market relations without confusing calling with title, recognition with oblivion, and duty with irresponsibility.

The anti-value orientation of a person in modern reality creates an unstable, unstable, moreover, disturbing existence. Therefore, it is so important to understand the significance and meaning of those value orientations that qualitatively transform human existence.

In modern axiology, such antipodes of values as anti-values, quasi-values, pseudo-values are also distinguished. It is these components of being that take away in a person, especially a young person, confidence in the future, plunging him into the world of chaos and "strange attractors" (uncertainty). The world of such antipodes determines inhumane aspects in human consciousness, thus influencing civilizational development.

Anti-values act in social, socio-natural being, as well as in interpersonal relations of mankind. For example, if we talk about the so-called quasi-values, which are especially popular in the modern transforming world space, it is important to note the fact that they penetrate into all spheres of human existence and its activity - science, family, culture, education system, upbringing and others. «Quasi-values are a special, specific reality of human culture, individual and social consciousness, which include errors, delusions, prejudices, illusions, myths, deceit and similar phenomena. They exist like our prejudices, unreliable, unconfirmed and unverifiable information. They can be massive (like treatment on TV), have professional "manufacturers", "technologists", prophets and give rise to their own special organizations or social institutions»[1, 131].

These phenomena observed today offer us their surrogates for truth, goodness, beauty, justice and, existing in society, lower the quality of human life and sharply narrow the possibilities of a person with their ambiguous existence. Vivid scenes of sophisticated murders, violence, and others, we constantly see on the screens of our TVs, social networks that we use. This raises questions, in particular, in what kind of cruel and hostile existence do we exist? Indeed, it is precisely such scenes that determine the appearance in the human mind of such anti-value reference points as aggression, enmity, hatred, and anger. They exist in the cognitive apparatus of human consciousness, harming him and his surrounding reality.

The danger of quasi-values, pseudo-values is that, posing as a value, they bring destruction to the human value world. They always ultimately prevail over the positive phenomena of life,

especially when a person is captured by religious beliefs and it is sometimes very difficult for him, captured by these illusions, to get out of it on his own and improve his life.

The emerging anti-value reality is now being confirmed in a society in which super-incomes, material wealth, entertaining, not always moral content on social networks are important, for which people receive huge sums of money, while work in the public sector is losing its value in the eyes of young people. Young people are eager to earn money quickly and easily. Also, anti-values are reflected in a person in the form of drug addiction, alcoholism, deviant behavior, the spread of pornographic plots and motives in various spheres of human existence. This has a very destructive effect on such a fundamental value as human health and future.

So, today we are in a polysemic world, in which values should be focused on the preservation and development of the world, human life, predicting the future of the planet, strengthening moral principles, technological and innovative development of the world. «The idea of building a society with high ideals is a key challenge facing the modern transforming Uzbekistan»[2, 334].

The world of anti-values can be neutralized to some extent or even transformed into values, but this is the opinion of a few. It is officially considered that the negative processes in this area and their overcoming lie on the paths of the democratic development of countries, national, economic and cultural upsurge, the development of science and education, the strengthening of the legal foundations of society and the systems of collective and international security. At the same time, the fact becomes obvious that order in the country and around the world begins with order in one's family and in one's own home, and to settle things with the environment near one's house, street, entrance - this is to bring order to the whole world. Here, love for the Motherland, both small and large, is an important value: «The process of forming and consolidating the spirit of patriotism among citizens is the basis with the function of preserving the socio-cultural code of the peoples of Central Asia, including the Uzbek people»[2, 335].

However, the value consciousness of modern Uzbek society as a whole, and especially of young people, has changed a lot. The life situation forces a modern person, sometimes consciously, and more often unconsciously, to make a meaningful choice for himself in a particular life situation, and therefore, to come into contact with value or anti-value realities, which, thanks to the volitional efforts or lack of will of the individual, enter his life and accompany him through it. . The obvious facts of modern life in its value dimension are the strengthening, cultivation and familiarization with universal human values. People need them, because in the communication of really intelligent and cultured people there is no acute problem in communicating with each other. Their culture and intelligence presuppose devotion to the highest intellectual, moral and aesthetic values of mankind: «... the principle of the priority of universal human values is not just a good wish and a beautiful phrase, but an axiological imperative, realized by various areas of philosophical thought on the basis of already existing universal human values, without implementation of which humanity will cease to exist» [3].

If we turn to the ontological nature of values - to the stages of achievement and types of values, we consider it important to pay attention to the group of values that is given by the Leningrad School of Philosophers:

1. Symbolic;
2. Instrumental;
3. Final.

The final value is those spiritual axiological landmarks that a person ultimately strives for. Such values are love, attention, victory, happiness, etc. In order to achieve the final value, for example, victory, a person goes through the stage of instrumental values, that is, that through which he achieves victory. It can be training, agility, constant, professional sports and participation in competitions in which a person wins. Symbolic values in this example can be flowers, a medal, a cup and other material things.

Today, the attitude to values has been transformed. This trend is associated with numerous factors: changes in social, technological, political, economic conditions and much more. At one time,

E. Fromm noted that such values as individuality, compassion, love, responsibility, mercy, officially recognized, quite conscious values in democratic countries, are in fact perceived by many people as a manifestation of ideology. Such value orientations, being moral norms, do not have a real impact on a person. Moreover, the attitude towards such values as property in its various manifestations, consumption in various forms, the significance of social status, as well as entertainment and physical pleasures, has become completely different. In our opinion, such a mixture or substitution of axiological guidelines determines irreparable damage, will lead to a fall in values and a depreciation of relations between people.

The study of value is a manifestation of the value attitude to the objects of being and involves subjective assessments in which the process of cognition is associated not only with understanding and explanation, but also with the interpretation of meanings. An attempt to evaluate, attribute to value, reveal the essence of the value itself takes place within the value field of being, in which the analysis of value phenomena occurs not without the influence of the human personality. Thus, we come to understand value as a complex, multifactorial phenomenon, the internal feature of which is many-sided and heterogeneous, and its external manifestation is complex and ambiguous.

The study of the ontological foundations of values shows that they contain a certain attitude of a person to the world, the general orientation of life attitudes and needs of the individual depends on them. Important for a person of any age, and especially a young one, is the assimilation of socially significant values that underlie the process of socialization and occur under the influence of such powerful institutions as the family, the education system, the interaction of people and direct contact with each other, labor and civic activity. Such changes can be a socio-cultural process aimed at changing and transforming the systems of people's value consciousness, and this leads to a change in their mass consciousness and behavior. Especially these changes hurt the ethno-cultural traditions of all peoples without exception. Any tradition preserves and reproduces patterns of thinking and behavior, assessments and ways to resolve conflicts, standards of beauty and social roles of the sexes. All this is subject to depreciation and transformation in the modern world.

In modern Uzbek society, the tension is quite obvious, expressed in mutual oppositions between the old basic and new, mostly instrumental values, which are used to some extent by all people. The planting of new forms of being by the methods of administrative pressure has always proved to be ineffective and not so much helped as hindered the introduction of social life into practice. These methods of pressure also gave rise to adequate resistance of the population, strengthening the desire to preserve cultural traditions, their ethnic self-identification and a negative attitude towards innovations.

Another problem that is gaining momentum is the problem of human-environment relations, which is clearly manifested in cities. The current generation is an eyewitness and the main culprit of the impoverishment of species diversity and the disappearance of plant and animal species, that is, the deterioration of the state of the first nature, accompanied by the breakage of trophic chains that connect one organism with another. Restoring extinct species is very difficult, if not impossible. That is why genetic diversity is an important condition for the normal functioning of all natural systems, the death of each next species reduces the stability of the biosphere and increases the likelihood of destruction of biocenoses. Thus, problems of a planetary scale have been created by human "civilization" - the problem of space debris, pollution of the world's oceans, etc. On the contrary, for a modern person, money, property, power and information are values that have taken place in his life and are quite significant values. A person as a person in modern conditions cannot fully exist without these components. But it was they who became in society either objects of vices and transformations, or aimed at health, prosperity, independence and well-being.

Modern trends in the world are such that even the dominant and fundamental values in society are amenable to rethinking and even transformation, especially for those who are trying to succeed in their business, looking for success in life or advantages in new living conditions, thereby trying to self-identify themselves.

A modern person is forced to live in a polysemic world, in which personal and planetary values on the basis of universal human values and their guidelines become a priority, capable of self-

organization and self-identification in order to understand others in their own aspirations in this complex and far from stable world of information space. Orientation to the polysemic world and its possibilities becomes for a person the only stable axiological formation on which he can rely in the rapidly changing world of global problems.

The information society in which we live, as a product of the development of a post-industrial society and globalization, is a natural historical process that cannot be stopped by a person. The result of this development is the formation of a single axiosphere (value sphere) of universal human culture, and on its basis of personal and planetary values in the poly-value world, in which the integrity and fullness of human life is preserved. In this aspect, the thoughts of the thinker-encyclopedist of the Muslim Renaissance Abu Reihan al-Biruni are interesting, who «in his work “India”, in the chapter “On the division of the Chatur Yuga into four Yugas and on conflicting opinions on this issue”, arguing about the fourth Yuga, gives the causes and consequences of the extinction of the first three civilizations (South), which he called the "Golden Clan", which replaced the "Silver Clan", and his third - the "Bronze Clan". Biruni considered the main criterion for the existence of civilization to be justice, which gradually left people, they became greedy, envious, evil, stingy, which subsequently led to the crisis of their civilization»[2, 335]. So, we see that an important socio-cultural code that will save all of humanity from degradation is creative value orientations.

With the development of means of communication in the information space, the spiritual shell in this space is able to reach planetary scales and influence people. In this regard, personal and planetary values form the axiosphere of the polysecular world, the ontological foundations of which are able to give stability to the personality and create advantages in the information space.

The inner shell in the axiosphere of the poly-value world is those ontological foundations of personal values and their guidelines that contribute to the formation and development of personal qualities in a person.

These ontological foundations are, first of all, profession and creativity, culture and religion, traditions and customs, habitat and place of residence, science and professional competence, scientific and economic knowledge, and others. Their formation and development in human life is a complex process. The personal level of polyvalues in modern conditions of life is constantly undergoing transformation, devaluation and depreciation and cannot take place without two limits: self-identification and communication-network, forcing a person to reconsider his life attitudes and value priorities in modern reality.

The outer shell of the axiosphere of the poly-value world is associated with planetary values, which include tolerance and spirituality, peace and life on planet Earth, the stability of biospheres and geospheres, and much more, without which not only personal development, but also human survival is problematic. The planetary level of polyvalues is aimed at:

- a) self-organization of the communicative and civilizational space of a person in a huge field of communication with different cultures;
- b) overcoming the disunity of society, which is provoked by competitive struggle in the modern world;
- c) neutralization of negative tendencies caused by competition at different levels, whether it concerns the arms race or the protection of the vital interests of citizens of different countries;
- d) the preservation of planet Earth from its destruction, since the negative results of human activity cause concern all over the world: on the planet Earth itself, and in the oceans, and in outer space[5].

Another important problem of the ontological foundations of value orientations is the issues of culture shock, in which many people of the post-Soviet period have been in our country, and many young people cannot cope with it now, when they return from other countries, where they radically change their value orientations. . An active and enterprising person is more in demand in the information space, and he is preferred in our time. He is able to master the latest technologies and the "phenomenon of meeting" with innovations for him becomes a place for discovering himself and applying his abilities aimed at the development and well-being of society. Such activities do not always meet with the support of those people who remain true to the values of traditional culture and

are in no hurry to change their axiological guidelines. Their fear of losing what is dear to them also does not find understanding in society.

The interaction of the personal and planetary levels of the axiosphere of the polysecular world of this value model, its connection with various value coordinates, aimed at customs, traditions, culture, education and self-identification, can make a person stable, balanced to any innovations and transformations in life, help him at any age have a decent life.

Both the inner and outer shells in the axiosphere of the politic world of the human personality contribute to the acquisition by mankind of a sustainable path for further development and become the ontological basis of its life activity and life support. At present, the ontology of value orientations is the stability of spheres (structures, frameworks, models) corresponding to universal human values, and on their basis, personal and planetary values in their interaction. And if universal human values always serve the ideals of the world, then personal values characterize the connection of a person with the external environment, while planetary values ensure the existence of stable shells of ideals aimed at preserving the planet Earth in its unique form.

The study of the ontological foundations of the axiosphere of the polysecular world of the human personality convinces us that their reliability is directly related to the personality of a person. The devaluation of values and their guidelines is associated with a subjective beginning and is completely controlled by the person himself, while the transformation of values and their guidelines is an objective process that is difficult to control by a person, but the strength of a human personality lies in predicting these processes, their mitigation in people's lives. Personal and planetary values in close connection with universal human values in the axiosphere of the polysecular world can form a fundamental, complementary system. Its stability can be ensured by close interaction with the identification and communicative-network limits of the human personality, the definition of axiological (value) coordinates that can restore the integrity of individual "Selves", violated by the fast pace of modern life, and overcome the disunity of society through the development, preservation and diversity of new forms of communication.

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ДАННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ПОДГОТОВЛЕН К ИЗДАНИЮ В РАМКАХ
ИННОВАЦИОННОГО НАУЧНОГО ПРОЕКТА № А-ОТ-2021-11 "СОЗДАНИЕ
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